

COMPUTER SCIENCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13969360>

APPLICATION OF COMPUTER TECHNOLOGY IN BUILDING A NEW MODEL OF TRAINING METHODOLOGY

Summary:

The article discusses the structure of the management system and methodological support, taking into account the requirements of modern education to improve knowledge and skills.

Keywords: Languages of artificial intelligence, development of a prototype system, learning tools

The inclusion of information processes in the structure of education, informatization of the educational process requires new qualities from all educators. This, in turn, implies the acquisition of new skills and habits. Training and improvement of ICT staff in the education system includes:

- Reconstruction of the system of teacher training for secondary schools, taking into account the concept of informatization of education;
- Establishment of a management and methodological support system to improve the knowledge and skills of education system employees in the field of ICT. Development of relevant programs to increase ICT literacy of various categories of educators (primary school teachers, subject teachers, school administration). The improvement of subject teachers should not be limited to teaching the use of ICT equipment, but should also focus on inculcating practical skills to integrate existing resources into the teaching process;
- Organization of computer literacy courses for other subject teachers in their schools by computer science teachers with the required level of training;
- Adequate assessment of the work of subject teachers and computer science teachers using ICT, development of a system of stimulation and motivation of their activities;

- Taking into account the results in stimulation and motivation measures by holding various competitions and contests among subject teachers;

- Development of more flexible programs for the improvement of computer science teachers;

- Training of trainers to accelerate the improvement process;

- Establishment of relevant institutions ;

- Information and methodological centers for the training and improvement of ICT in education in the regions;

- Ensuring regularity and systematization in the process of improving educators in the field of ICT;

- Introduction of new specialties related to informatization of education in the system of higher, secondary specialization and technical vocational education. In this sense, let us note the development and definition of a new model of modern training through Expert Training Systems. The creation of an Expert Training System is one of the most important issues for the development of educational software.

Expert Training System (ETS) is a complex software package that combines, disseminates and uses the scientific knowledge and experience of highly qualified specialists in the field of education and training.

User interface - a set of software that implements a dialogue between the user and ETS in the process of entering the request and receiving a response.

The logical result block is a program that models the flow of expert opinions based on the information in the knowledge base.

An explanatory subsystem is a set of software that answers the following types of user questions: How was this or that recommendation received? Why did the system make such a decision? The first question refers to the full course of the opinion, showing all the relevant fragments of the knowledge base, and the second

question refers to the judgment that precedes the conclusion obtained.

Intelligent Knowledge Base Editor is a program that allows a knowledge engineer to create a knowledge

base in dialogue mode. This includes a built-in menu system, a template for the language in which the knowledge is presented, a "help" mode and other services that make it easier to work with the database.

Each classification element has a purpose and characteristics. For example, the learning system corrects mistakes and shows the correct answer when learning any subject (subject) by computer; analyzes the weaknesses of the learner in the field of the subject and develops tools to overcome them; Determines the amount, volume and degree of complexity of knowledge transfer, depending on the degree of mastery. An example of such a system is the PROUST system for Pascal's teaching. They aggregate (adapt) standard application software packages (eg, mathematical statistics, linear programming, or database management systems) and consist of software packages that are tools for knowledge manipulation. The application of hybrid systems can be a tool for solving complex problems related to the application of intellectual property (software) or expert knowledge for software envelopes. However, the development of hybrid systems is much more complicated than autonomous ES. Because combining software envelopes with different methodologies creates a number of theoretical and practical problems.

Instrumental tools for the development of ES have also been developed. They can be divided into 4 groups:

1) Traditional programming languages (C, C +, Basic, Small Talk, Fortran, etc.). It is mainly designed for numerical algorithms, and requires a lot of work from the programmer due to the lack of ability to work with symbols and logical data. However, these languages are well adapted to traditional machine architecture.

2) Artificial intelligence languages - the most common are Lisp and Prolog. Their universality is lower than traditional programming languages, but they have a wide range of possibilities for working with symbols and logical data. Special computers are created on the basis of artificial intelligence languages (for example, Lisp - machine). These languages are not used in the development of expert training systems.

3) Special software tools - provide the development of educational programs at a higher level than artificial intelligence languages.

4) Covers - Cover means a ready-made version of the ES, which does not have a knowledge base. Covers eliminate programming processes in the creation of ESs. In this case, only a specialist working in the subject area is required to fill the knowledge base with real data. Library - It is difficult to use covers for informational knowledge bases. Because modeling a number of processes is very complex (eg, abstracting, bibliographic and analytical review, etc.).

The technology of creating educational software is almost the same as the model technology for the development of individual ETS for the entire education system. Currently, experts divide the development of ETS into six consecutive logical stages:

1. Identification of issues in the field of education;
2. development of a prototype system;
3. Bringing the development of ES to the level of operation;
4. evaluation of the expert training system;
5. system coordination;
6. system support.

Identifying problem areas and issues is important for all stages of ETS. The head of the ETS, ie the knowledge engineer, must identify the problem. An unfavorable problem can be a waste of time and money if selected. The knowledge required to solve the problem must also be stable, accurate and relatively constant and cover all relevant issues.

The development of a prototype system is a generalized version of ETS. A prototype system is a special project designed to verify the accuracy and coding of facts, judgment strategies, and relationships between

objects and processes provided by an expert. The prototype project consists of dozens of rules, frames and examples.

Experimental methods of knowledge selection (discovery) were explained as a method of direct live dialogue between a knowledge engineer and an expert. But this is not the only method. At present, the methods of selection (discovery) of knowledge to create knowledge bases are given:

For example, let's build a computer model to calculate the square root of odd numbers out of 5 to 95 natural numbers.

1. Construction of the algorithm of the given problem

2. Execute the program of the problem in Pascal programming language

3. Implementation of the developed program on the computer

Since the block diagram of the algorithm is methodologically understandable, let's compile it.

Program SF;
 Uses crt;
 Var x:integer;
 S:real;

Begin S:=0;
 For x:=5 to 95 do begin
 If x mod 2 <> 0 then s:=sqrt(x);
 Writeln ('s',s);
 End;
 End;

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